

Pooling cohorts for deep learning analysis: a potential source of bias for electrocardiogram analysis

Marie Mørch-Pedersen^a, Malene Nørregaard^a, Claus Graff^b, Oliver B. Vad^c, Pia R. Lundegaard^d, Jesper Hastrup Svendsen^{c,e}, Torben Hansen^f, Allan Linneberg^{e,g}, Peter G. Jørgensen^h, Magnus T. Jensen^{e,i}, Peter Rossing^{e,i}, Christina Ellervik^{e,j,k}, Dominik Linz^{l,m}, Vajira Thambawitaⁿ, Mary M. Malekar^o, Michael A. Riegler^o, Jørgen K. Kanters^{a,p}, Jonas L. Isaksen^{a,*}

^a Laboratory of Experimental Cardiology, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

^b Department of Health Science and Technology, Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark

^c Department of Cardiology, Copenhagen University Hospital – Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen, Denmark

^d Cardiac Genetics Group, Department of Biomedical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

^e Department of Clinical Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

^f Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Basic Metabolic Research, Denmark

^g Center for Clinical Research and Prevention, Bispebjerg and Frederiksberg Hospital, The Capital Region, Copenhagen, Denmark

^h Department of Cardiology, Herlev and Gentofte University Hospital, Copenhagen, Denmark

ⁱ Steno Diabetes Center Copenhagen, Herlev, Denmark

^j Department of Laboratory Medicine, Boston Children's Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA

^k Department of Clinical Biochemistry, Zealand University Hospital, Køge, Denmark

^l Department of Biomedical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

^m Department of Cardiology, Maastricht University Medical Center, Maastricht, the Netherlands

ⁿ SimulaMet, Oslo, Norway

^o Simula Research Laboratory, Oslo, Norway

^p Center for Biosignal Research, University of California, San Francisco, San Francisco, CA, USA

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ABSTRACT

Background and Objectives: Deep learning models can isolate device characteristics in medical images, enabling the models to identify the origin of a medical image, which creates a bias. It is unknown whether such bias can arise with raw medical signals such as electrocardiograms (ECGs), so we aimed to quantify to what extent deep learning models can identify the study cohort and site from which an ECG originates.

Methods: We used 70,075 12-lead ECGs from four Danish cohorts and the UK Biobank. We trained a convolutional neural network (CNN) model using 5-fold cross-validation to identify the origin of each ECG. We also tested the effect of easy vs. difficult to predict outcomes (sex vs. diabetes) and equal vs. skewed outcome distributions. We reported accuracy and F₁ score, which is less sensitive to unequal sample sizes.

Results: The CNN model was able to distinguish ECGs from five different cohorts with an accuracy of 93.4% and an F₁ score of 77.1%. We found no bias with easily detected outcomes or equal distributions. We were unable to ascribe the CNN performance to any known factors, including ECG device, software, or population characteristics, including sex, age, and comorbidities.

Conclusions: Deep learning models can identify the origin of an ECG. Combining studies can introduce confounding to the model if the rate of the outcome varies between studies and the outcome is difficult to identify. In deep learning models with potential cohort confounding, we recommend training a baseline model to separate these cohorts to assess the strength of confounding.

* Corresponding author at: Department of Biomedical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Nørre Allé 14 2200, Copenhagen, Denmark.

E-mail address: jonasisaksen@sund.ku.dk (J.L. Isaksen).

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1. Introduction

There are good reasons for combining multiple cohorts when training deep learning models. Using more training samples improves performance and reduces the risk of overfitting, and a larger variety in training data improves generalization [1]. However, studies have found that deep learning models can identify the hospital of origin for medical images by isolating subtle differences in acquisition protocol, image processing, or distribution pipeline [2,3]. If the outcome rate varies between hospitals, the model may then learn to identify where an image comes from rather than what is on the image and still get apparently reasonable results. This is a problem because the model does not solve the intended task, and external validation with a new dataset is required to even identify the problem [3].

In epidemiological terms, this problem is called confounding and happens when the outcome rate differs between the individual cohorts. In the most extreme scenario, ‘cases’ and ‘controls’ have been simply taken from separate cohorts [4–6].

Confounding in deep learning can occur if the cohorts are easier to identify than the outcome. The electrocardiogram (ECG) is a highly standardized medical time series with a high signal-to-noise ratio [7]. The electrocardiographs produced by a few global vendors implement tightly regulated digital filters, and recordings are performed by trained personnel using worldwide standardized lead placements, most often after a period of rest [7,8]. Furthermore, ECG research uses the raw ECG tracings and not images of the ECG [9]. Consequently, *a priori*, we consider the ECG unlikely to contain any cohort-identifying traits.

However, to our knowledge, no one has tested whether confounding by cohorts can influence deep learning-based ECG analysis. Therefore, we aimed to quantify the extent to which the combination of multiple ECG cohorts can bias the results of deep learning models.

2. Methods

2.1. Populations

We included participants with digital ECGs from five different population studies. Participants provided written informed consent.

The Danish General Suburban Population Study (GESUS) was carried out between 2010 and 2013 with participants from selected postal codes in Næstved Municipality located 80 km south of Copenhagen, Denmark [10]. People with Danish citizenship aged 18 years or older were eligible for inclusion. Digital ECGs were available from 8,675 participants. Participant information is based on answers from a validated questionnaire.

The Inter99 [11] study from the baseline health examination in 1999–2001 is a Danish study with participants selected as a random sample from the Danish Civil Registry in the age group 30–60 years from 11 municipalities in the south-western part of Copenhagen. Digital ECGs were available from 6,661 participants. Participant characteristics were obtained from questionnaires and nation-wide registers (International Classification of Disease, 8th revision [ICD-8] and 10th revision [ICD-10]).

The UK Biobank (UKB) is a large study, with in-depth genetic and health information, from half a million free-living UK participants aged 40–69 years and living in the UK [12]. From this study, we used 52,793 ECGs from the first imaging visit, obtained at one of four assessment centers in Bristol, Cheadle, Newcastle or Reading between after 2014. ECGs were recorded after rest in the supine position according to a standardized protocol [13]. Information on the assessment center was missing for 1509 people with ECGs, who were excluded from the assessment center analysis. Patient characteristics were based on questionnaires and UK Biobank field 1712 “first occurrences of diseases”. The UK Biobank was accessed under application number 43247.

The Thousand&1 study was conducted in Gentofte, Denmark between 2010 and 2012 and included 1,093 type 1 diabetes patients aged 18

years or older, without any known heart disease [14]. Participants were included from the Steno Diabetes Center. Digital ECGs were available for 921 patients and were collected with a single device. A detailed questionnaire was part of the examination.

The Thousand&2 study was carried out in Denmark between 2011 and 2013 at Steno Diabetes Center, and Herlev and Gentofte Hospital [15]. 1,025 digital ECGs were available from 1,030 included participants with type 2 diabetes. A detailed questionnaire was part of the examination.

From all studies, we recorded the ECG device, software version, and sampling rate. We recorded the following comorbidities, the prevalence of which may vary by population and which may manifest on the ECG: Prior acute myocardial infarction, prevalent ischemic heart disease, hypertension, and diabetes [16–20]. Comorbidities were based on questionnaires and register entries (see the [Supplementary Method](#) for details).

2.2. Electrocardiograms and standardization

All ECGs were 10-second 12-lead ECGs recorded using GE electrocardiographs (GE Healthcare, Wauwatosa, WI). ECGs in all cohorts were sampled at 500 Hz with CardioSoft or MAC-5500 electrocardiographs and processed on a dedicated research MUSE server (GE Healthcare, Wauwatosa, WI). All ECGs were re-analyzed using version 2.43 of the 12SL algorithm (GE Healthcare, Wauwatosa, WI) to make measurements comparable between cohorts. From the MUSE server, we exported a median beat as delimited text files at 500 Hz.

We excluded ECGs with missing leads and ECGs that had been deemed noisy prior to this work in a semi-automatic approach with manual review of noisy candidates.

2.3. Deep learning model and implementation

We adapted the convolution-based model by Hicks et al. which was developed to exploit and learn novel features from ECGs [21]. We removed the early average pooling layer to keep the high fidelity and used global max pooling instead of average pooling in the last hidden layer. These modifications improved performance only slightly. The architecture of the model is shown in Fig. 1. The convolutional neural network (CNN) was fed a single 1.2-second representative median heartbeat sampled at 500 Hz (i.e. a dimension size of 600x8).

We trained the model *de novo* to classify the origin of an ECG using five-fold cross-validation. No patient was included in both training and validation of any model instance. We used two sets of outcomes: 1) Cohort (GESUS, Inter99, Thousand&1, Thousand&2, UKB [irrespective of center]) and 2) UKB center (Bristol, Cheadle, Newcastle, Reading).

Fig. 1. Architecture of the CNN used for all experiments. Red “Conv” blocks are 1D-convolutional layers, blue “BatchNorm” blocks are batch normalization layers, and beige “ReLU” blocks are rectified linear unit activations. The green “GMaxPooling” block is a 1D global maximum pooling. The model contains 8 identical gray “ResBlock” residual network blocks with skip connections (additions). The prediction layer used a softmax activation.

We investigated both pair-wise classification (binary outcome with pairing data sources two at a time) and multiclass classification with classification of all classes collectively.

All models were implemented in Python v3.10.12 using TensorFlow v.2.8.0. We used a batch size of 128, the Adam optimizer and a learning rate of 0.00001. The model was trained for a maximum of 1000 epochs or until no progress was observed for 100 epochs.

2.4. Comparator model

As a reference we designed a Comparator model. The Comparator model predicted origin randomly with a class probability equal to class prevalence. This approach to random guessing maximizes the F_1 score, which ends up equal to the proportion for each class (e.g. the Comparator model would get a F_1 score of 0.75 for a class comprising 75% of the cases). The Comparator model corresponds to a model that learns the distribution of the training set – and nothing else – and applies that knowledge to the test set, making it a suitable baseline as a model that cannot infer origin from the cohorts.

2.5. Use case

To show the implications of bias in matching cohorts, we designed a use case similar to a previous study [4]. We included all people from the Thousand&2 cohort and included controls without diabetes from the GESUS cohort. We trained a model of identical architecture to Section 2.3 *de novo* to identify diabetes based on only the raw ECG from the mixed cohort using 5-fold cross-validation. We then applied the model to ECGs from the UK biobank, with people with and without diabetes. If the model detects diabetes, we expect a similar performance, whereas if the model identified the dataset, we expect a drop in performance on this external validation dataset. We reported sensitivity, positive predictive value (PPV), and the F_1 score for the detection of diabetes in the use case.

2.6. Delineation of confounding

The use case fulfills two requirements: An imbalanced distribution (0% vs. 100%) and a target (diabetes) which is difficult to derive from the input (ECG). To illustrate that both these factors are requirements for the confounding to happen, we conducted two-by-two scenarios with and without class imbalance and with an easy and a difficult target. The difficult target was diabetes as in the use case and the easy target was male sex. Deep learning models have consistently identified sex with a high accuracy before [21,22]. The use case scenario remained the same, and we used the GESUS and Inter99 cohorts for the remaining scenarios. We used the UK Biobank as the validation cohort in all scenarios.

2.7. Statistics

We performed both pair-wise classification and multi-class classification. To evaluate the model's performance, we used the metrics of accuracy, sensitivity, PPV, and F_1 score.

Accuracy is the overall proportion of correct model predictions to total predictions. For each class, the ratio of successful predictions is weighted proportionally to the class size, thereby largely disregarding the performance of the minority class. This causes accuracy to yield misleadingly high performances for class-imbalanced data [23].

The F_1 score handles imbalanced data better than accuracy by combining the PPV and sensitivity of the model ($F_1 = 2 * \frac{PPV * sensitivity}{PPV + sensitivity}$) [24]. We used the macro-averaged F_1 score – the unweighted mean of F_1 scores across all classes – to reduce multiclass prediction to a single metric.

We present summarized confusion matrices (cross-tabulation of the actual and predicted classes) across all five folds, whereby each row in

the matrix represents an actual class and each column represents a predicted class. The diagonal thus represents correct predictions.

Statistics were conducted in R v4.1.2 (The R Foundation, Vienna, Austria).

3. Results

3.1. Populations

The five cohorts contained a total of 70,075 ECGs from both men and women from Denmark and the United Kingdom. The populations were on average quite similar in terms of sex, age, BMI, and comorbidities – except for the Thousand&2 cohort which had more males, higher BMI, and more prevalent heart disease (Table 1).

3.2. Pair-wise classification

We performed binary classification to identify what cohort an ECG originated from for all pair-wise combinations of cohorts, and the results are given as macro averaged F_1 scores in Table 2 and accuracies in Supplementary Table S1. Across all cohort-pair combinations, the average F_1 score was 84 ± 6 % and the average accuracy was 93 ± 7 %. The F_1 scores ranged from 71% (telling apart Thousand&2 and UKB) to 94% (Inter99 and UKB), with most pairwise results ranging between 77% and 86%. All confusion matrices are listed as Supplementary Table S2.

3.3. Multiclass classification

The performance of the multiclass classification of the five cohorts is presented in Table 3, and the confusion matrix is presented as Supplementary Table S3. On average, the F_1 score was 77.1%, and the accuracy was 93.4%. However, there were important variations between cohorts, with F_1 scores for the individual cohorts ranging from 50.9% (Thousand&2) to 97.3% (UKB).

The comparator model, which learned only class distribution (cohort sizes), by comparison, achieved much lower scores with an averaged F_1 score of 20.0% and an accuracy of 59.2%.

3.4. UKB center identification

Participants at the four centers displayed similar average characteristics (Supplementary Table S4). In the multiclass classification of the four assessment centers in the UKB data, the model was able to identify the correct center in 59.8% of cases (Table 4). The F_1 scores ranged from 15.1% (Bristol, the smallest center with 5.3% of participants) to 72.3% (Cheadle, the largest center with 55% of participants) and averaged at 42.9 %. The confusion matrix is presented as Supplementary Table S5.

The comparator model, by comparison, achieved an F_1 score of 25% and an accuracy of 38.7%, well below the CNN accuracy of 59.8%.

3.5. Use case

The use case represents a clinically relevant scenario, where a model is trained on two cohorts (with low [0%] and high [100%] prevalence) to identify ECGs from patients with diabetes (Graphical Abstract and Fig. 2, upper right panel). In the cross-validated training of the model, we saw an F_1 score of 71%, which may lead one to believe that the model, to some extent, can separate diabetes patients from control based on the ECG. However, in the external validation with an independent cohort, we saw a drop in performance down to an F_1 score of 10%. We saw corresponding drops in sensitivity and PPV. This step was necessary to show that the model is unable to separate people with and without diabetes, and that it is more likely that the model identified cohort origin instead.

Table 1
Baseline characteristics for the five cohorts at the time of electrocardiogram recording.

	GESUS	Inter99	Thousand&1	Thousand&2	UK Biobank
Population size, N	8,675	6,661	921	1,025	52,793
Female sex, %	54%	49%	48%	34%	51%
Age, years	57 ± 14	46 ± 8	49 ± 15	64 ± 10	65 ± 8
BMI, kg/m ²	27 ± 5	26 ± 5	25 ± 4	30 ± 6	27 ± 5
Prior myocardial infarction, n (%)	198 (2.3%)	34 (0.5%)	0 (0%)	113 (11.6%)	1,243 (2.4%)
Ischemic heart disease, n (%)	622 (7.3%)	80 (1.2%)	0 (0%)	237 (23%)	3,287 (6.2%)
Hypertension, n (%)	942 (11.0%)	18 (0.3%)	505 (56%)	875 (90.0%)	16,226 (31%)
Any diabetes, n (%)	347 (4.0%)	42 (0.6%)	921 (100%)	1,025 (100%)	2,352 (4.5%)
Heart rate, beats per minute	65 ± 11	67 ± 11	73 ± 13	76 ± 13	62 ± 11
QT interval, ms	409 ± 30	403 ± 27	393 ± 31	390 ± 33	419 ± 31
Acquisition Device (Electrocardiograph)	MAC-5500	CardioSoft	CardioSoft	CardioSoft	CardioSoft
Acquisition SoftwareVersion	009C & 010A	V6.7X6	V6.61	V6.61	V6.73
Sampling rate, Hz	500	500	500	500	500

Mean ± standard deviation and n (%) are shown. BMI, body mass index

Table 2
F₁ scores for the separation of electrocardiograms from two cohorts. Higher numbers (max 100%) indicate better separation of cohorts. The model could separate electrocardiograms much better than chance (50%) for all pairs of cohorts.

Cohort	Thousand&1	Thousand&2	GESUS	UK Biobank
Thousand&2	84.0%			
GESUS	85.8%	83.7%		
UK Biobank	85.3%	71.2%	92.2%	
Inter99	78.9%	85.6%	76.6%	93.8%

3.6. Delineation of confounding

Two factors underlie the use case and are requirements for the confounding to happen: 1) The target is more difficult to discern than cohort origin and 2) the prevalence between two or more cohorts varies greatly. We found that when only one of these factors is present, no confounding happened (Fig. 2). Prediction of the difficult target of diabetes using mixed cohorts lead to confounding with imbalanced prevalence, but not with similar diabetes prevalence in the cohorts. For the relatively easier prediction of male sex, class imbalance did not confound the results materially. We found an F₁ score of 82% in the

Table 3
5-class separation results. The model separated electrocardiograms from the five cohorts much better than chance in terms of sensitivity, positive predictive value (PPV, precision), F₁ score, and accuracy.

Cohort	N (%)	Convolutional Neural Network				Comparator (balanced guessing)			
		Sensitivity	PPV	F ₁	Accuracy	Sensitivity	PPV	F ₁	Accuracy
GESUS	8,675 (12.4%)	85.1%	84.3%	84.9%		12.4%	12.4%	12.4%	
Inter99	6,661 (9.5%)	82.7%	82.7%	82.7%		9.5%	9.5%	9.5%	
Thousand&1	921 (1.3%)	66.1%	73.6%	69.6%		1.3%	1.3%	1.3%	
Thousand&2	1,025 (1.5%)	48.2%	53.9%	50.9%		1.5%	1.5%	1.5%	
UK Biobank	52,793 (75.3%)	97.4%	97.2%	97.3%		75.3%	75.3%	75.3%	
Summarized	70,075	76.0%	78.4%	77.1%	93.4%	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%	59.2%

PPV, positive predictive value.

Table 4
Electrocardiogram-based identification of the UK biobank study site. The model was able to identify the site of recording with an F₁ score (42.9%) much better than chance (25%). Site information was unavailable for 1,482 participants, who were excluded from the site identification study.

Assessment Center	N (%)	Convolutional Neural Network				Comparator (balanced guessing)			
		Sensitivity	PPV	F ₁	Accuracy	Sensitivity	PPV	F ₁	Accuracy
Bristol	2,706 (5.3%)	10.5%	26.7%	15.1%		5.3%	5.3%	5.3%	
Cheadle	28,389 (55.3%)	80.5%	65.6%	72.3%		55.3%	55.3%	55.3%	
Newcastle	10,303 (20.1%)	31.6%	46.0%	37.5%		20.1%	20.1%	20.1%	
Reading	9,913 (19.3%)	43.1%	51.3%	46.9%		19.3%	19.3%	19.3%	
Summarized	51,311	41.4%	47.4%	42.9%	59.8%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	38.7%

PPV, positive predictive value.

balanced scenario and 84% in the imbalanced scenario.

4. Discussion

Using convolutional neural networks and ECGs from more than 70,000 individuals from 5 cohorts, we found that combining ECG cohorts for deep learning models can introduce a significant level of confounding. With a clinically relevant use case, we showed that a model that identifies the cohort of origin instead of the intended target has an F₁ score of not 50% but rather somewhere between 80% and 90%. This level of bias was much higher than what could arise from differences in cohort size. The results demonstrate that, despite heavy standardization in recording ECGs, residual cohort-specific characteristics are embedded in the raw ECG signals and can be exploited by deep learning models. Our use case demonstrated that the bias can be difficult to identify without a validation cohort.

4.1. Clinical characteristics

We included ECGs from five population studies with different scopes. The Thousand&2 cohort notably differs from the other cohorts across several parameters that may be reflected in the ECG, including a higher proportion of male participants [22,25] and higher age [26], slightly

Fig. 2. How diagnostic difficulty and class imbalance in combination lead to confounding. Bottom left: Male sex is a relatively easy task for the model to identify, which is reflected in the high F₁ score. The small drop in performance on validation is typical for this setup. Top left: The model does not benefit substantially from trying to learn cohort origin in the imbalanced scenario because it is easier to derive sex than cohort. Bottom right: It is difficult for the model to discern whether a patient has diabetes based on their electrocardiogram (ECG) alone, as reflected by the low F₁ score. Top right: In the imbalanced scenario, the model learns cohort origin instead of diabetes because this is easier and leads to better perceived performance. However, external validation shows a dramatic drop in performance and reveals the inability of the model to detect diabetes.

higher BMI [27], and a larger prevalence of heart disease and hypertension [28], higher heart rate, and the highest prevalence of type 2 diabetes [20]. Likewise, the Thousand&1 cohort included only patients with type 1 diabetes and without heart disease, which may also be reflected in the ECG [18,19]. However, we did not find that these cohorts were easier to tell apart from the others, and as such it is unlikely that known clinical characteristics drove the classification. Consequently, factors other than clinical characteristics probably drive the cohort identification.

4.2. Technical factors

We did not find that populations with ECGs recorded in different electrograph models were better separated than populations with ECGs from the same model. In fact, ECGs from the Thousand&1 and Thousand&2 cohorts were obtained using one and the same device, but these cohorts were as separable as any other two. Thus, we cannot explain the findings by comparing the differences in electrocardiograph models or settings.

4.3. Standardized protocol within UKB

All UKB centers use the same device model and software and follow identical procedures, which should minimize operator variability. This increased homogeneity in data may explain the lower accuracy compared to the cohort identification task. However, even under these extreme attempts at harmonizing between sites, the model was able to distinguish site origin in the ECGs much better than chance. Thus, some cohort-identifying traits persist encoded in the ECG even with extreme standardization.

4.4. Possible explanatory factors

Although we did not identify an obvious explanation for why a neural network is able to distinguish ECGs from different cohorts, some factors are well known to affect the ECG and may play a role. A slightly damaged cable may appear as increased noise in one or more leads, and room electrical shielding can directly affect the noise level on the ECG.

Site-specific noise contamination can significantly degrade the quality of recordings [29]. Skin-to-electrode impedance values can be extremely variable and unpredictable [30], making it harder to obtain consistent, high-quality data across different patients.

Systematic differences in lead placement directly affect the ECG and may identify a site or even a technician. For instance, electrode misplacement is directly visible in the ECG recording and has been proven common in clinical settings [31,32]. If leads V1 and V2 are displaced more superior on the chest than the correct fourth intercostal space, the amplitude of the P wave diminishes. For placements even further superior, the P wave may become inverted, which also influences the estimation of P-terminal force [33,34].

4.5. Only a problem with machine learning

Although ECG-based epidemiology has been a huge field of research for years, it is straightforward to posit why this study was not made before. The heavy standardization around electrocardiographs, combined with reproducible machine-based reading of ECG markers [8], limited cohort-specific variations to the actual differences to the ECGs. In contrast, deep learning models are data-driven structures that need no hand-crafted features but perform feature extraction and processing in one go [35]. Thus, researchers do not decide what ECG features are used by deep learning models, which enables the model to latch onto previously unavailable cohort-identifying traits. These traits are processed as latent space features and are not humanly interpretable in a traditional sense. Thus, despite our best efforts, the lack of transparency makes it challenging to check exactly how the model works [36]. Classical epidemiologists would never use these unknown features and might even statistically correct for differences between cohorts in the analyses.

4.6. Confounding requirement

There are two requirements for the type of confounding that we presented in this work. First, this confounding can only happen if cohorts with different outcome prevalence are pooled in the development. Second, it must be easier for the model to identify cohort origin than the actual required target. Detecting male sex on an ECG alone is

difficult for a human expert, but it is easier for deep learning models [21,22]. We found no confounding when the target was easy to identify, which will be the case for many diagnostic and research purposes.

4.7. Recommendations

When cohorts are combined and the above-mentioned requirements are met, care must be taken to ensure that a promising F_1 score is not a result of hidden confounding. We found that F_1 scores up to 94% may reflect pure confounding in extreme cases. Importantly, in this work we showcased how researchers can test the strength of confounding and thereby show that their model is not fully confounded even when no external validation cohort is available. We also showed that a single large, diverse cohort with multiple sites is subject to less confounding than when different cohorts are combined. Potential strategies to counter this type of confounding include domain adaptation [37,38], adversarial training [39], and data augmentation strategies [40] specifically designed to obscure cohort-specific features while preserving task-relevant information.

Our findings suggest that the FDA guidelines on machine learning on ECGs are appropriate. [41,42] We have demonstrated that the potential bias is large enough to warrant adherence to the 10 guidance principles for good machine learning practice [43] and transparency [44] formulated by the FDA together with Health Canada and the United Kingdom's (UK's) Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency.

4.8. Limitations

The study used ECG tracings, and it is unknown if other medical time series such as electromyography and electroencephalography are also affected by confounding to the same extent when cohorts are pooled. We have assessed known confounders including sex, age, BMI, previous myocardial infarction, and hypertension, but we cannot rule out residual confounding owing to population characteristics. However, it is unlikely that any patient characteristic is a larger confounder than those assessed in the study. Because the hold-out validation set was used to stop training, the results of identification in the main analysis may theoretically be slightly overestimated [45]. However, the effects that we found are much larger than the potential bias and the differences often found between populations [21]. This study only used a CNN model and we are unable to generalize to other architectures.

5. Conclusions

Deep learning models can accurately identify the origin of ECGs from different populations and from different centers within a study. We could not ascribe this identification to known factors, including technical settings or population characteristics. This unintended identification gives rise to confounding if the rate of outcome varies between sites. The strength of confounding can be assessed by training a baseline model to separate the cohorts used.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marie Mørch-Pedersen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Malene Nørregaard:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Claus Graff:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Data curation. **Oliver B. Vad:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Pia R. Lundegaard:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jesper Hastrup Svendsen:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Torben Hansen:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Allan Linneberg:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Peter G. Jørgensen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Magnus T. Jensen:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Peter Rossing:** Writing –

review & editing, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Christina Ellervik:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Dominik Linz:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Vajira Thambawita:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Mary M. Maleckar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Michael A. Riegler:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Jørgen K. Kanters:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jonas L. Isaksen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2026.110424>.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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